

Waveguides for model-based sonification

Katharina Vogt

Institute for Electronic Music and Acoustics (IEM),
University of Music and Performing Arts Graz (KUG), Austria
vogt@iem.at

David Pirro

IEM,
KUG, Austria
pirro@iem.at

Robert Höldrich

IEM,
KUG, Austria
hoeldrich@iem.at

ABSTRACT

Digital waveguides have been used in signal processing for modelling room acoustics. The same technique can be used for model-based sonifications, where the given data serves to construct the three-dimensional sound propagation model. The resulting sounds are intuitive to understand as they simulate real world acoustics. As an example we introduce a digital waveguide mesh based on complex data of computational physics. This approach allows exploring sonically this three-dimensional data and unveiling spatial structures.

1. INTRODUCTION

The interdisciplinary research project QCD-audio [1] explored the use of sonification in computational physics. This field is a very notable fusion of theoretical and experimental physics, the so-called ‘tertium quid’ [2]. ‘Experiments’ are conducted within the computer, and have to be perceptualized in some way to access the information content that is generated. Usually, visualization is used at various stages of the process, from first de-bugging of code and a scanning through the data to the presentation of the final, usually highly aggregated results. One example of a simple visualization as used by physicists can be seen in Fig. 3.

Sonification provides an interesting alternative to visualization in this context for various reasons [3], e.g., physical data often spreads in time, which sound does as well, and such data are usually too high-dimensional to be fully visualized. Due to the various questions addressed and the data types and phenomena studied within the QCD-audio project, different sonification approaches have been developed. One of these is presented within this paper.

Model-based sonification [4] is an approach, where the data of a specified phenomenon are used to build a physical model, that can be seen as a virtual instrument. This model is then excited by any input, often specified by a user’s interaction. Waveguide meshes have been used in the context of model-based sonification by Lee et al. [5]. They explored two different approaches. First, a vocal tract model using digital waveguides provided an intuitive sound representation of data which is phoneme-based. In a second ap-

proach, multi-dimensional data was mapped onto waveguides, i.e., the sound propagation of an acoustic space was simulated as a mesh of transmitting and reflecting (and partly absorbing) sites. When the data affected the mesh size, the resulting sounds were barely distinguishable. On the other hand, when data was clustered and mapped to the impedance of the mesh (i.e., changed the reflection properties of neighboring sites), resonance zones were created that can be distinguished. This approach was tested with object identification in a two-dimensional ‘*game of Battleship*’. Two-dimensional waveguides proved to be less computationally demanding, but three-dimensional data more interesting.

We used a three-dimensional waveguide mesh, a standard physical model of a hollow body, e.g., applied in room acoustics. The approach is introduced in Sec. 2. The data set which is used in the sonification example is described in Sec. 3. The resulting sonification is explained in Sec. 4, and conclusions are drawn in Sec. 5. The system has been implemented in SuperCollider3 [6]. Listening examples can be found at <http://qcd-audio.at/results/qcd-waveguides>.

2. THE DIGITAL WAVEGUIDE MESH

The digital waveguide mesh is an efficient method of simulating wave propagation numerically. For an extensive introduction into the field see, e.g., [7].

In a linear waveguide, a one-dimensional wave $y(x, t)$ propagates along the space dimension x at speed c . This describes, for instance, the transverse displacement of a vibrating string or the longitudinal sound velocity in an organ pipe. Following the d’Alembert solution of the wave equation, the wave can be decomposed in a left-going (y_l) and a right-going component (y_r):

$$y(x, t) = y_r \left(t - \frac{x}{c} \right) + y_l \left(t + \frac{x}{c} \right) \quad (1)$$

Physical space is discretized as $x_m = mX$ in the digital waveguide model, and time as $t_n = nT$. The travelling wave solution is thus sampled at intervals of T seconds, with the spatial expansion then given by $x = cT$. The wave travels to the left or right one waveguide site per time sample. The sampled form of the traveling-wave solution is then given by:

$$\begin{aligned} y(t_n, x_m) &= y_r [(n - m)T] + y_l [(n + m)T] \quad (2) \\ &\equiv y^+(n - m) + y^-(n + m). \end{aligned}$$

The term $y^+(n - m)$ corresponds to the output of an m -sample delay line, with an input of $y^+(n)$; thus the wave-

Figure 1. A normalized scattering junction in the 1-dimensional digital waveguide model.

form is delayed by m samples. Correspondingly, $y^-(n+m)$ is the *input* to an m -sample delay line whose *output* is $y^-(n)$. The actual wave value (e.g., displacement or velocity) at each waveguide site is the superposition of the left- and right-going part.

In the ‘free-field’ case, an excitation triggered at some input site(s) n_i is propagated through the mesh as a wave without losses. If there are boundaries, or changes of the impedance, in the mesh, the wave is reflected at that point (partially) and the reflected part superimposes with the incoming wave. The impedances R_i at each site i result in the *reflection coefficient* $k_i(t)$ between adjacent sites in direction i ,

$$k_i(t) = \frac{R_i(t) - R_{i-1}(t)}{R_i(t) + R_{i-1}(t)}. \quad (3)$$

The effect of R changes its sign depending on the wave direction. E.g., for transversal wave propagation on a string, the relation between the physical force density (or *stress*) f_i and the velocity $v(t) = dy/dt$ is given by:

$$\begin{aligned} f_i^+(t) &= R_i v_i^+(t) \\ f_i^-(t) &= -R_i v_i^-(t) \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

Referring to Eq. (3), the stress can be derived for a normalized setting of variables (see [7, p. 358ff]), and f is now denoted with a tilde. The normalized lossless scattering junction is then the digital simulation of two neighboring sites with impedances R_i and R_{i+1} resulting in a reflection coefficient k_i :

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{f}_i^+(t) &= \sqrt{1 - k_i^2(t)} \tilde{f}_{i-1}^+(t - T) - k_i(t) \tilde{f}_i^-(t) \\ \tilde{f}_{i-1}^-(t + T) &= k_i(t) \tilde{f}_{i-1}^+(t - T) + \sqrt{1 - k_i^2(t)} \tilde{f}_i^-(t). \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

The simulation diagram of a 1d mesh is shown in Fig. 1.

This approach can be easily extended to two or more dimensions, resulting in a waveguide *mesh* as shown schematically in Fig. 2 for two dimensions [8]. At each junction, incoming and outgoing waves are summed (denoted by ‘+’) up to calculate the wave value.

Errors in digital waveguides stem from a small numerical error, and a larger dispersion error: higher frequencies have a higher propagation velocity than lower ones, due to the geometrical characteristics of the mesh.

Figure 2. Scheme of a digital waveguide mesh in two dimensions.

3. DATA

The data set was provided by the Institute for Physics of the University of Graz. A detailed explanation of the data set cannot be given here; please refer to [3] or [9]. At this point, we only discuss general properties of the data sets.

Figure 3. Clusters derived from the local Polyakov loop, an observable in QCD data. One cluster, the largest found in the data set, is depicted for each of the two different temperatures. Below the phase transition (*upper figure*), clusters are small. Even the largest cluster found does not percolate, i.e., connects opposing lattice sites. Above the transition (*lower figure*), the cluster does percolate. Visualization of the three-dimensional data set is difficult, even if only one state is depicted at a time (in this case, the one forming the largest cluster), and only one cluster is shown for each temperature. (Source: C. Gattringer)

Physics is often interested in phase transitions such as the transition from water to ice. There is also a phase transition in the description of the smallest known building blocks of matter - quarks and gluons. The field theory describing this phenomenon is quantum chromodynamics (QCD). A certain observable in the data set that physicists are interested in (the so-called Polyakov loop) shows different behavior above and below the phase transition. Clusters emerge, defined as sets of nearest neighboring sites having the same state (see Fig. 3). They are rather small in

a system below the phase transition. Only above the transition, when the system is in a different phase, the cluster *percolates*, i.e., fills the whole system, whose boundaries are periodically closed (thus one neighboring site of the first site is the last site in the lattice, which forms a torus.) The data are three-dimensional and occur in four different states ($-1, 0, 1$, and 2 ; the latter referring to undecided states which are ignored).

If the system has a percolating cluster and which size it is depends on the temperature at which the simulation is run. Standard physics methods run a whole set of configurations, started randomly, for each temperature and compute at which temperature the system usually exhibits a percolating cluster. Sonification of the data set allowed a more qualitative exploration of the cluster structure, as a visualization is not sufficient. The graphs in Fig. 3 communicate the idea of the studied phenomenon, but are not very useful in terms of data analysis. The small cluster is one random choice (many more clusters exist, but if they were shown, the picture would resemble the lower one). Also the specific shape of the cluster cannot be clearly seen. Even if the cluster percolates is not completely clear from the lower picture. We used waveguides for a sonification of the data set and wanted to see (i) if a cluster percolates and (ii) of which shape and size the clusters then are.

4. QCD WAVEGUIDES

Figure 4. Two schematic examples of the waveguide mesh, with clusters of the ‘grey’ states highlighted, excited by noise. As the left configuration is not percolating and the right one is, a sonification signal $\hat{y}(t)$ is recorded at the ‘southern’ end of the right configuration. The left configuration stays silent.

In our example, we implemented a 3d waveguide mesh. In the sonification approach, we used a model in which the clusters of each state (excluding the ‘2’) are regarded as tunnels of free wave propagation; the borders of the tunnel are defined as hard reflections between different states. The tunnels are excited by white noise or by an impulse at one side of the lattice, and the resulting resonant signal is

Figure 5. Examples of a 20^3 sites waveguide mesh, excited with an impulse (all values set to one) at time $t = 0$, and run for 20,000 samples. Three percolating tunnels of different sizes were programmed into the mesh as ‘test clusters’: from a 1 sample-tunnel over the whole length to a square tunnel of 15 times 15 samples over the whole length of the mesh. Small tunnels lead to the excitation of high frequencies. These decay quickly. Due to longer distances of free wave propagation between hard reflecting boundaries of the cluster, large tunnels lead to lower frequencies. Both waveforms and sonograms are depicted for the three showcases.

recorded at the opposite side. The sound signal propagates through the lattice only if there is percolation.

We use the concept of a sonification operator to explicitly describe our sonifications based on a general, mathematical formulation, see [3]. The sonification operator for this example of a model-based sonification (MBS) is given in Eq. (6).

$$\hat{y}(t; x_n, y_n) = MBS[Impulse(t_0; x_0, y_0)](t) \quad (6)$$

The readout condition is to sum over all sites of the ‘southern’ boundary plane ($[x_n, y_n] \equiv [x, y, z] |_{z=0}$) of the mesh for all times, e.g., 30,000 samples. Two different excitation inputs have been used at time 0 at the opposite, ‘northern’ plane ($[x_0, y_0] \equiv [x, y, z] |_{z=n}$): one is a locally distributed ‘noise’ or random values, the other an impulse, where all boundary values are set to 1. The model is defined by free wave propagation inside the clusters/ tunnels, and hard boundaries between them. A schematic plot is shown in Fig. 4.

The waveguides are computationally demanding and are calculated in non real-time. For each physical state, a separate waveguide mesh is calculated. The three resulting soundfiles are played simultaneously on three channels or mixed in stereo to the left, the middle, and the right position. It is very unlikely that more than one state will show percolation. Thus, only the left, middle or right channel

plays, and the assignment of the percolating state is unanimous.

For presentation purposes we implemented simple showcase examples, where an impulse was used as excitation input, that are presented in this paper. Real data examples are less obvious, especially when plotting their waveform or spectra, but can be found on the homepage. Test clusters, i.e., simple ‘tunnels’ extending from north to south, with three varying cross-sections were created. The resonances in the sonification signal are determined by characteristic sizes of the tunnel. The smallest tunnel of 1x1x20 mesh sites loses its energy quickest, thus the sound decays, and the higher frequency components are the most distinct; see Fig. 5.

Sound is only generated, if the cluster percolates, which is the most important fact physicists are interested in. Furthermore, the sound gives information on shape and size of clusters, because this is what determines the resonances that are excited, the decay behavior of the sound and, overall, the resulting timbre. Sound examples for the test tunnels as depicted in Fig. 5 can be found on the homepage, <http://qcd-audio.at/results/qcd-waveguides>:

5. CONCLUSIONS

We presented a special kind of model-based sonification, that builds on waveguide meshes. The model is based on simple physical principles, thus easy to understand and communicate. The sounds are intuitive and can be analyzed by untrained listeners building on their everyday experience on how hollow bodies and rooms sound, depending on their size and shape. Listening tests with physicists or other domain scientists would be an obvious next step. The suggested sonification gives information about aggregated behavior of systems, in this case clusters of the same state in the data set, rather than sonifying each data point separately. Therefore, the sonification is very efficient, and large data amounts can be played within a short time.

The disadvantage of the use of waveguide meshes in sonification is having a long computation time. The system is not apt for data exploration where quick interaction with the system, e.g., changing data sets and other settings, is necessary. While physicists usually focus on gathering information from many different runs of the simulation, the sonification allows for a more qualitative exploration of single, typical, data sets. A further disadvantage of using this approach in sonification is that the data set is ideally only composed by a few distinct categories (states) of values, or can be easily grouped into such.

Still, many data have the right pre-conditions for using them as input of a waveguide sonification. We are planning to further optimize the program in terms of calculation time, and use it on different types of data sets such as provided by climate research.

Downloads

An SC3 class for waveguides can be downloaded from <http://qcd-audio.at/results/qcd-waveguides>.

Acknowledgments

We want to thank Christof Gatteringer from the Institute for Physics, University of Graz, for the great collaboration. The work has been funded within the Translational Research Project *QCD-audio* by the Austrian Science Fund (FWF), <http://qcd-audio.at>.

Comment

Parts of this paper have been published within the thesis of K. Vogt [3].

6. REFERENCES

- [1] Qcd-audio research project. [Online]. Available: www.qcd-audio.at
- [2] P. Galison, *image and logic. A material culture of microphysics*. The University of Chicago Press, 1997.
- [3] K. Vogt, “Sonification of simulations in computational physics,” Ph.D. dissertation, University of Music and Performing Arts Graz, 2010.
- [4] T. Hermann, *Sonification for Exploratory Data Analysis*. Technische Fakultät der Universität Bielefeld, 2002.
- [5] K. Lee, G. Sell, and J. Berger, “Sonification using digital waveguides and 2- and 3-dimensional digital waveguide mesh,” in *Proceedings of the 15th International Conference on Auditory Display, Limerick*, 2005.
- [6] J. McCartney, “Rethinking the computer music language: Supercollider.” *Computer Music Journal*, vol. 26, no. 4, pp. 61–68, 2002.
- [7] J. O. Smith, *Physical audio signal processing for virtual musical instruments and digital audio effects*. Center for Computer Research in music and Acoustics (CCRMA), August 2006. [Online]. Available: <https://ccrma.stanford.edu/~jos/waveguide/>
- [8] S. A. VanDuyne and J. O. Smith, “Physical modelling with the 2-d digital waveguide mesh,” in *Proc. of the International Computer Music Conference, Tokyo*, 1993, pp. 40–47.
- [9] C. Gatteringer, “Coherent center domains in SU(3) gluodynamics and their percolation at T_c ,” *arXiv:1004.2200v1*, 2010.